

YOGA IN MODERN LIFE TO PROMOTE WORK-LIFE BALANCE

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“ Where there is a will, there will be a way”

Abstract

Modern life has become full of challenges, stress, aggression, depression, which are disturbing the entire life, as a result it is leading to an unpleasant environment in both the personal life and work life.

It is an need of the hour to reduce these negative outcomes to bring prosperity and Work Life Balance in one's life. Work life balance is maintaining harmonious relationship between work life and personal life. Time management, Stress management, setting boundaries for work, flexibility in work will be some strategies to maintain work life balance.

Yoga is a mantra that can be followed to overcome the above challenges. It is an ancient practice to have mental strength, healthy body, flexibility and reduced stress.

Organizations also identified the effectiveness of Yoga in balancing work life of employees to reduce work stress, to make them react less and act more, improve mental clarity and improve focus and other benefits. Present paper focuses on the impact of Yoga in work life balance of individuals working in different sectors like teaching, IT, banking and other private organizations.

The objectives of the present study are

1. To analyse the effectiveness of Yoga practices in promoting WLB.

2. To identify the barriers of incorporating yoga into life style.
3. To study the perception of individuals on yoga practices.

The present study considers both Primary and Secondary data for the analysis. Primary data is collected by administering questionnaire to the employees of different sectors. Secondary data is collected from journals, previous researches, books and internet. The study is limited to only working people in different fields

Key words : Yoga, Work-Life-Balance, stress management, personal life, work life

I. INTRODUCTION:

It is important to balance the human life with both work and personal time. In this fast-paced world, there is no time to take care of our own health and time. If there is no alternative to do this, it becomes difficult to have the overall wellbeing. Integrating Yoga in the routine life will enhance the work life balance. Though practice of Yoga is individual's personal and it is their unique way to follow, it shows impact on the mental and physical health. It is a spiritual discipline to achieve harmony in life. It is very important to adopt yoga in modern life because it makes us stay active, focused, relieve pain, manage stress. In this modern life style, stress has become the integral part of every one irrespective of age and position. Stress in the work for employees makes them exhausted, aggressive or create symptoms of depression. A person who experiences high work stress will not be able to manage his personal life too. Stressors may arise from anywhere like work place, family, relationship etc but they are to be managed to keep us effective. People realised the significance of Yoga in managing stress and balancing mind. Today we can find many Yoga centres, different sources to learn Yoga both online and off line also available after the pandemic. Yoga aasanas and stretches relieve the pain caused because of work. Yoga is being followed in schools and offices too to relieve stress, to keep fit and healthy. The benefits of yoga are unfolding and being suggested even by the doctors and experts to practice Yoga regularly rather than spending cost on medication and health care.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To analyse the effectiveness of Yoga practices in promoting Work Life Balance.
2. To identify the barriers of incorporating yoga into life style.
3. To study the perception of individuals on yoga practices

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The present study considers both Primary and Secondary data for the analysis. Primary data is collected by administering questionnaire to the employees of different sectors. Secondary data is collected from journals, previous researches, books and internet. The study is limited to only working people in different fields. This study considers simple random sampling for collecting data from 198 respondents working in different industries.

NEED AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Work is inevitable in human life and when there is work it is very common for the involvement of stress. Coping with the work stress for balancing professional and personal life is very important for every individual. In order to mitigate stress in modern life and maintain Work Life Balance, adopting Yoga and practicing it would be the wise option rather than spending lot on medication and health care. For this reason, organizations are also conducting Yoga and meditation sessions to make the employees focus more on their work. Stressed employees are likely to transfer their work stress to other employees and as a result all the work place gets disturbed. So some of the organizations are providing Yoga at work place to provide relief for the employees from work stress. This helps in increasing productivity, employee retention, reduction in absenteeism and helps in many other ways to maintain flexibility and mindfulness. Practicing simple Yoga techniques in the routine life keeps the body and mind relaxed. Researches identified the impact of Yoga on maintaining Work Life Balance. 20min practice of Yoga will enhance lot of focus and decrease the stress. In corporate setting, increased focus translates to better decision making. Yoga originated as an ancient Indian method of maintaining physical and mental health. It is called as spiritual science

and improves psycho physiological condition. It improves cognitive process and acts as opposite to stress and so provides Work Life Balance.

The present paper highlights the role of Yoga in promoting Work Life Balance in the modern world. The present study is limited to working people in different industries. Its scope includes impact of Yoga on the WLB of the employees in their modern life styles.

II REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

- ❖ According **Siddappa Naragatti**, in his research “**The study of Yoga on Health**”, in International Journal of Innovative medicine and Health Science, vol 12, April 2020, ISSN 2056-9866. He concludes in his study that Yoga is adopted in daily life to maintain good health and also helps in prevention of psychological stress. Yoga practices helps in attention of focus and instils greater amount of relaxation and peace of mind.
- ❖ According to **Ch. Sri Sai Ratna and Bhanu Priya Dwarapudi**, in their research “**Impact of Yoga Practice on Work Life Balance of women managers – A study in selective organizations**” in Internal Journal of Management, Vol 14, Dec 2023 online ISSN 0976-6510. They opined in their study that Yoga practices help reduce stress because they promote relaxation and acts as the opposite to natural stress. Stressful work environment leads to irritation, concentration difficulties, stomach ache and other problems. The entire world believes that practice of Yoga asanas in human life help to strengthen body and dhyana will improve our focus which is most needed for the individual in the modern life. They conducted research globally and its results helped to prove that Yoga practices helped to improve Work Life Balance.
- ❖ According to **Shivam Dubey, Shiv ji Malviya, Hemalata Pant, Er Pradeep Kushwaha** in their research “**A Review of Yoga practice and its effects**”, **Challenges and opportunities in Nutrition, Environment and Agriculture, March 2022**, opined that Yoga offers a powerful technique for overseeing and diminishing pressure, tension. Yoga builds blood stream and levels of haemoglobin and red blood platelets, takes more oxygen. Yoga diminishes

danger of coronary failure and stroke. They also concluded that considering logical proofs, it is reasonable to infer that Yoga can be useful in the counteraction and fix of sicknesses.

- ❖ According to Yatendra Kumar Sharma, Sushil Kumar Sharma, Ekta Sharma in their study “Scientific Benefits of Yoga – A Review”, in International Journal of Multi-disciplinary Research Review, 3(8): 144-148, August 2018. Their opinion in their study is physical and mental benefits of Yoga makes it ethically questionable to assign participants to inactive control groups. Yoga sessions are to be conducted for cost effectiveness and for daily practice.

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

ANALYSIS OF AGE OF RESPONDENTS

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
20-30	20	10.10
30-40	101	51.01
ABOVE 40	77	38.88
TOTAL	198	100

Source : Primary data

Interpretation : Most of the employees are belongs to 30-40 years of age.

Obj 1: To analyse the effectiveness of Yoga practices in promoting Work Life Balance.

There is an impact of Yoga in maintaining Work Life Balance	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
YES	138	69.69
NO	12	6.06
MAY BE	48	24.24
TOTAL	198	100

Source : Primary data

Interpretation :

It was observed from the data that most of the respondents responded that there is an impact of Yoga in maintaining Work Life Balance

Obj 2: To identify the barriers of incorporating yoga into life style.

Barriers to adopt Yoga by for you in daily life	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1. Lack of time	102	51.51
2. Lack of motivation	66	33.33
3. Physical limitations	28	14.14
4. Other reasons	2	1.01
Total	198	100

Source : Primary data

Interpretation :

It is observed that most of the respondents are lacking time or failing to set proper time to do Yoga daily. 33.33% of respondents are lacking motivation to do Yoga daily.

Obj 3. To study the perception of individuals on Yog

PERCEPTION OF INDIVIDUAL ON YOGA	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yoga is physical exercise	118	59.59
Yoga is a stress relief	45	22.72
Yoga is a spiritual practice	30	15.15
Total	198	100

Source : Primary data

Interpretation :

Most of the respondents perception is that Yoga is physical exercise. Some people 22.72% are feeling it as stress relief practice. Few others i.e 15.15% are thinking Yoga as a spiritual practice.

CONCLUSION:

Yoga is a powerful tool to relieve stress promote work life balance in this modern life style. Practice of Yoga asanas will relax the body and improve mental and physical health. When there is an enhancement in the physical and mental health, there will be a better decision making possible by the individuals, this helps to have a Work Life Balance. Yoga is to be identified as an important practice to be incorporated in every one's life in the modern life styles, where work stress is inevitable. It was observed from the data collected that most of the respondents are having a opinion that Yoga has an impact on the Work Life Balance. There are challenges observed to adopt Yoga in the routine life like lack of time, lack of motivation, physical or body related limitations like injuries, pain etc. These challenges can be faced with slow practice i.e 10-15 min of Yoga practice and slowly the time can be increased based on the opportunity. Most of the people's perception about Yoga is observed as an exercise. Yoga is not just an exercise, it is also spiritual science if followed regularly, will be able to mitigate stress and improve cognitive thinking to balance the Work Life.

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